

Tailoring the Properties of a Shape-Memory Polyurethane via Nanocomposite Formation and Nucleation

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Figure S1. DSC traces showing heating (a, c; rate = 10 °C/min) and cooling cycles (b, d; rate = 5 °C/min) of the neat PU (a, b) and 15% w/w PU/CNC nanocomposite (c, d). All cooling cycles were followed by an isothermal rest at 20 °C for time intervals of 30, 60 or 90 min. All cycles started with the first the heating trace and involved samples that had previously been stored at ambient conditions for at least 2 days.

Figure S2. DSC traces showing heating (a, c; rate = 10 °C/min) and cooling cycles (b, d; rate = 2 °C/min) of the neat PU (a, b) and 15% w/w PU/CNC nanocomposite (c, d). All cooling cycles were followed by an isothermal rest at 20 °C for time intervals of 30, 60 or 90 min. All cycles started with the first the heating trace and involved samples that had previously been stored at ambient conditions for at least 2 days.

Figure S3. Wide-angle X-ray diffractograms of the neat PU, a PU mixture containing 1% w/w of dodecanoic acid and a 15% w/w PU/CNC nanocomposite containing 1% w/w of dodecanoic acid.

Figure S4. Size-exclusion chromatography traces of the neat PU and the melt-processed PU mixture containing 1% w/w of dodecanoic acid. The calculated M_n , M_w and \bar{D} are 110,000 g/mol, 229,000g/mol and 2.08 for the neat PU and 19,600 g/mol, 66,300 g/mol and 3.38 for the PU nucleated with 1% w/w of dodecanoic acid.

Figure S5. DSC traces showing the first heating and cooling cycles (rate = 10 °C/min) of the neat PU and a solution-cast film of a PU/1%w/w dodecanoic acid mixture.

Figure S6. Shape-memory stress-strain-temperature curves (three consecutive cycles) of the 5% w/w PU/CNC nanocomposite (a) and the 10% w/w PU/CNC nanocomposite (b). Experiments were conducted with a fixing temperature of 10 °C. All cycles started with programming at 70 °C; after the samples had been kept at this temperature for 5 min the samples were strained until a strain of ~40% was reached by applying a force at a rate of $0.8 \text{ N} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. Keeping the stress constant, the samples were subsequently cooled to and kept at the respective fixing temperature for 5 min before the stress was removed and the samples had adopted their temporary shapes. The shape recovery was subsequently triggered by heating the samples to 70 °C and keeping them at this temperature for 10 min.

Figure S7. Shape-memory stress-strain-temperature curves (three consecutive cycles) of the neat PU (a, b), the PU and 15% w/w PU/CNC nanocomposite nucleated with 1% w/w dodecanoic acid (c, d). Experiments were conducted with a fixing temperature of 5 °C (a), 10 °C (b) or 20 °C (c, d). All cycles started with programming at 70 °C; after the samples had been kept at this temperature for 5 min the samples were strained until a strain of ~40% was reached by applying a force at a rate of 0.8 N·min⁻¹. Keeping the stress constant, the samples were subsequently cooled to and kept at the respective fixing temperature for 5 min or 15 min (for PU at 10 °C) before the stress was removed and the samples had adopted their temporary shapes. The shape recovery was subsequently triggered by heating the samples to 70 °C and keeping them at this temperature for 10 min.